

MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI TARIXIY-MADANIY MEROSGA HURMAT RUHIDA TARBIYALASH

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Annotation: In this article, the importance and tasks of the formation of national pride in the process of familiarizing preschool children with historical monuments, as well as the importance and tasks of raising children in the spirit of national pride and respect for the historical and cultural heritage. We can teach preschool children about our historical and cultural heritage during classes or outside of classes, even by organizing excursions and virtual tours.

Key words: historical and cultural heritage, national pride, national pride, values, patriotism, historical monuments, excursion, virtual tour, competence approach.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni tarixiy obidalar bilan tanishtirish jarayonida milliy g'ururni shakllantirish, shu bilan birgalikda bolalarni tarixiy-madaniy merosga hurmat va milliy iftixor ruhida tarbiyalashning ahamiyati va vazifalari ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga mashg'ulotlar davomida yoki bo'lmasa mashg'ulotlardan tashqari vaqtlarda, hattoki, ekskursiyalar, vertual sayohatlarni tashkil etish orqali ham tarixiy-madaniy merosimizni o'rgatishimiz mumkin.

Tayanch so'zlar: tarixiy-madaniy meros, milliy g'urur, milliy iftixor, qadriyatlar, vatanparvarlik, tarixiy obidalar, ekskursiya, virtual sayohat, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv.

"Primary tasks have been defined to create conditions for intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children in all aspects, to introduce innovations, advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the preschool education system. This research work serves to improve the methodical system of developing interest in the past in children in the process of developing interactive means of raising national pride in preschool children, introducing them to historical monuments.

To protect and preserve the ancient and rich cultural heritage of our country, to promote its incomparable contribution to world culture and history at the international level and to expand cooperation in this regard, to draw the attention of the general public to this area, to create convenience for residents and tourists April 18 - the International Day of Preservation of Monuments and

Historical Places is widely celebrated in our republic every year. Public attention on this day focuses on various aspects of cultural heritage and the importance of its preservation at the international level. On the eve of the International Day of Preservation of Monuments and Historical Places, republican pageants and various other events aimed at attracting the attention of the general public, as well as representatives of the sphere of effective activity and active participants of the events, are duly encouraged.

In the process of introducing historical monuments to children of preschool age, the formation of national pride in pupils can be expressed as follows:

1. Analysis of the pedagogical possibilities of historical monuments in the formation of national pride in students;
2. Improving the model of formation of national pride in students in the process of introducing them to historical monuments;
3. Development of technologies for formation of national pride in students;
4. Improving the processes of providing students with a virtual trip to historical monuments.

Based on the historical experiences in the education of children, the people created a whole, integrated system of education. The importance of training was emphasized. Folk proverbs are appropriately used in education based on this method. The need to have qualities such as honesty, truthfulness, and goodness, to feel dignity, duty, and responsibility, was taught through admonitions. Advice is also often used in fairy tales. Because fairy tales are a school of life, in them the result of advice, the solution manifests itself. The method of setting an example is also widely used in the national values of the Uzbek people. In the epic "Ravshankhan" father, old woman, and brothers have all positive qualities, and we can see an example of humanity.

Later, words such as virtual world, virtual world, and virtual friend appeared. The meaning of the word virtual is to imagine. A virtual library is an abstract version of a regular library. The books, magazines and journals of this library are not on the bookshelves, but in the computer memory. It is a set of data stored in a digital format on a computer or special computer devices. These are: printed audio, video and multimedia data. Depending on the size of the data, the servers consist of one or several computers connected to the network.

When we introduce preschool children to historical monuments, we should not only teach them about our rich history, but also raise them in the spirit of respect for history. What hardships and hardships our people have gone through until today, how our people with a thousand-year history have been patiently

and steadfastly protecting their homeland, how our ancestors fought without leaving their country despite the hardships, and during the war there was not even a single piece of bread to eat. We should be able to show as an example that the people lived with hope for tomorrow. This should be an example not only for young people, but also for adults. After all, it is impossible to build the future without studying the history.

While educating preschool children in the spirit of respect for historical and cultural heritage, we should be able to instill in them a sense of national pride and pride. For this, we need to start focusing on the developing child in the mother's womb. After all, as the child develops in the mother's womb, his attitude towards the environment also increases, he also begins to enjoy nature and its beauties and blessings, now he is also a soul, he is also a person. Therefore, the feeling of affection and love for each other, which started in the family, later awakens a sense of pride for the motherland, and begins to look at history in order to build the future. Later, the child begins to step into the educational institution from home to school, where he acquires up to 70% of knowledge, now the feeling of national pride and pride begins to awaken in him, if he is directed to good education and upbringing. Therefore, we have to start the education and upbringing of the child from the family.

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